

HeSANDA for Health Cohort Studies

Program Guidelines

Version 1.1

3 July 2024

Program overview

The Health Studies Australian National Data Asset ([HeSANDA](#)) program is building national infrastructure to allow researchers to share and access data from health studies, including clinical trials, cohort studies and other data valuable for research.

HeSANDA is a foundational component of ARDC's health infrastructure portfolio - the [People Research Data Commons](#) which is addressing Australia's core digital health data challenges - and aims to create [FAIR data assets](#) from health studies.

Based on previous workshops with the Australian health cohort research community (read the report [here](#)), ARDC now seeks to:

1. Develop a national platform to support discovery of Australian health cohort studies and their data assets
2. Develop a national community of practice to support Australian health cohort study data practices and culture
3. Develop community-agreed national metadata standards for health cohort studies
4. Uplift the consistency of data policies and practices across health cohort studies

The new projects will build upon the highly successful model established with the [clinical trials community](#) that created a partnership of over 70 research organisations and led to the creation of the [Health Data Australia](#) platform and a range of other resources to support the national research community.

After establishing the FAIR Assets activities, ARDC will consider opportunities to extend the infrastructure capability of Australian health studies in the other focus areas (Secure Access, Integration, Analytics), to coordinate health studies with our other key communities (Government Data and NCRIS), and deliver applied projects in Disease Areas and Health Service Improvement.

Call for registrations of interest

We are seeking registrations of interest from eligible research or research-enabling organisations in Australia looking to participate in the delivery of the HeSANDA for Health Cohort Studies projects. This is not an invitation to submit proposals for projects at this stage. We are seeking an indication of interest and capability to partner in this program of work. The development of project proposals and partnerships will be facilitated by ARDC through a series of workshops beginning July 2024 - please register for the workshops [here](#). If you are unable to attend the workshops or for further information please email contact@ardc.edu.au.

Program outcomes

To meet the objectives of the program, ARDC is proposing two stages of work:

Stage One (Project delivery: Jul 2025 to Dec 2026)

An initial set of projects which will:

- A. Make health cohort data assets discoverable in Health Data Australia, and include a set of exemplar assets
- B. Design the requirements to extend Health Data Australia's functionality to provide measure-level discovery of cohort data (including consensus requirements for cohorts themselves to implement common approaches to measures and population variables).
- C. Identify key barriers to sharing of health cohort data and its inclusion in Health Data Australia and develop a scope of work that could address these barriers

Stage Two (Project delivery: ~Jul 2026 to Mar 2028)

A second set of projects which will implement the designs and scoped activities from 1(b) and 1(c).

The identification of specific projects and partnerships for both stages will occur via a facilitated process led by ARDC as summarised below (see 'Process and timeline').

Note: [Previous workshops](#) identified additional opportunities for ARDC to partner with health cohort studies including:

- Development/support for utilising trusted research environments
- Increasing the analytics capabilities of cohort research
- Improved access and use of government data for cohort study research

These opportunities are out of scope for this specific program but are directly in scope for other ARDC programs that will progress sequentially or in parallel to this program of work. These opportunities align with ARDC's broader health infrastructure portfolio (the [People Research Data Commons](#)) - see the figure below.

Figure - People RDC portfolio structure: The HeSANDA for Health Cohort Studies projects will partner with the health studies community to undertake work in the FAIR Assets focus area

The figure above represents the structure of ARDC’s People Research Data Commons portfolio with each square representing one or more projects or programs. Across the portfolio, ARDC will develop infrastructure in the four Focus Areas (FAIR data assets, secure access, data integration, and advanced analytics). Infrastructure projects will be established with Target Communities (health studies, government, and national infrastructure facilities) in accordance with Frameworks developed by ARDC with the sector. In the later stages, the exemplar projects will bring together the new infrastructure capabilities in Applied areas. As such, the ‘HeSANDA for Health Cohort Studies’ projects address the FAIR Assets objective for a subset of the Health Studies community. Further ARDC opportunities for the cohorts community in secure data access, data integration, and advanced analytics will follow in coming years and will be coordinated with existing projects.

Program details

Scope

The details of projects will be developed via the co-design process described below (see ‘Process and timeline’) but would broadly consist of some combination of the following:

In-scope activities

- Design, development, and documentation of systems for managing health cohort metadata and data sharing requests
- Development of underpinning infrastructure
- Development of data policies and procedures
- Preparation and publication of health cohort metadata
- Outreach resources and events to drive awareness and uptake of the infrastructure (e.g. training workshops, materials, etc)
- Co-design activities to build consensus for the Stage 1 items

Out-of-scope activities

- Academic activity (e.g. conference travel, manuscript production, etc)
- Collection of research data
- Infrastructure development that does not directly support the functions of a Health Data Australia or the program outcomes

Process and timeline

The process for developing and undertaking [Stage 1 \(a\), \(b\), and \(c\)](#) projects is as follows:

<p>1. Project Shaping</p> <p>Jul 2024 to Oct 2024</p>	<p>ARDC will work in collaboration with potential delivery partners and stakeholders to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. build an understanding of the current state of the activity area and opportunities for improvement B. identify and select potential solution(s) C. finalise the project team(s) who will deliver the solution(s)
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<p>1. Project Planning</p> <p>Nov 2024 to Feb 2025</p>	<p>ARDC will work in collaboration with project teams to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. develop an investable project plan including timeline, deliverables, co-investment, and resourcing B. collect feedback on the plan from key stakeholders C. finalise the project plan
<p>2. ARDC Endorsement</p> <p>Mar 2025 to Jun 2025</p>	<p>ARDC will review the finalised project plan. Subject to that review, ARDC will issue a draft legal agreement with the lead partner named in the approved project plan, and arrange for related payments to be completed once the agreement is executed by the relevant parties.</p>
<p>3. Project Delivery</p> <p>Jul 2025 to Dec 2026</p>	<p>The project team will complete the items specified in the approved project plan in accordance with the executed legal agreement and the project requirements specified below.</p>
<p>4. Outcomes & Impact Assessment</p> <p>Jan 2027 to Jun 2028</p>	<p>ARDC and/or the project partners will evaluate and report on the project's outputs, intended outcomes, and long term impacts as agreed to during the previous stages.</p>

Eligibility

Australian research organisations, universities, government departments, and publicly funded research organisations may apply. Interested parties who do not or are unsure whether they meet this criteria can contact ARDC to discuss further.

Investment and duration

The total ARDC budget for the program is \$1.5m over 3 years which includes all components of both Stage 1 and Stage 2.

ARDC policy requires a minimum of 1:1 co-investment ratio between ARDC's investment and that of all the other project participants combined. Both cash and in-kind co-investment are acceptable (see the [ARDC's Co-investment Guidelines](#) for details).

Project requirements

- Projects must be aligned with the [NCRIS 2023 Guidelines](#) and the Principles set out in the [NRI Roadmap](#) (pg 14 pdf, pg 21 doc)
- Projects must match ARDC's co-investment at a minimum 1:1 ratio between. Both cash and in-kind co-investment are acceptable. All co-investment must be made in an auditable form (see the [ARDC's Co-investment Guidelines](#) for details).
- The project budget should include all costs to successfully deliver the outcomes.
- Projects must have a dedicated project manager with appropriate experience and capacity. Depending on project needs, ARDC may require the naming of a specific Technical Lead and Research Lead.
- Projects must have a steering committee or project management group with defined Terms of Reference that meets at least quarterly¹. ARDC will provide a representative for the committee or group. The primary purpose of the committee/group is to review the progress of the project (scope/schedule/budget/risks/issues) and inform ARDC's monthly reporting requirements (see below). The terms of reference may be expanded (or a separate committee/group convened) to discuss other issues (e.g. strategy, technical issues, etc) - this is at the discretion of the project lead and is not a formal ARDC requirement.
- Projects are required to commit to monthly traffic light reporting and other reporting requirements specified at contracting.
- Project outputs should be made as FAIR as possible. See the [guideline for FAIR data](#).
- Project plans must include the tracking of desired outcomes, including measuring the uptake of infrastructure by the research community.
- Project teams are expected to collaborate with other People RDC and ARDC supported projects
- Project teams are expected to attend and contribute to ARDC workshops and events
- Project teams are expected to engage in communication activities to raise awareness of their infrastructure and attract a growing user base within the intended research community.

¹ The frequency of meetings will be decided during the formal project proposal stage